

K-waves of global GDP per capita (1961–2024) and GCR intensity extremes (1959–2022): $R^2 = 0.86$

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Abstract. The classical theory of innovation clusters (J. Schumpeter) and the concept of new technological paradigms (S. Yu. Glazyev), which dominate modern macroeconomics, view the emergence of fundamental innovations as the root cause of long waves (K-waves). However, these models leave a key question unanswered: what determines the cyclical nature of innovations and technological paradigms?

This paper proposes an interdisciplinary approach to the nature of long waves. A mathematical model of macrocycles is constructed based on a comparison of data from the Moscow Neutron Monitor on the intensity of galactic cosmic rays (GCR) for 1959–2022 and econometric statistics from the World Bank on global GDP per capita growth for 1961–2024.

The author has identified a very strong correlation between the peak GCR intensity and large business waves (K-waves), where the coupling of processes intensifies to a functional level ($R = 0.92$).

Unlike J. Schumpeter, who associated cycles with the discrete, wave-like introduction of innovations, and N. Kondratiev, who explained them by the renewal of fixed capital, the author demonstrates that the cyclical nature of innovation is a consequence of periodic changes in the **productivity of the human brain**. Minimum GCR intensity is accompanied by maximum solar activity and, with an average lag of two years, maximum geomagnetic activity, which desynchronize alpha waves in the brain and reduce the collective cognitive potential of the human population.

Forecast: The author has developed a method for forecasting K-waves of annual growth in global GDP per capita based on the forecast of the Wolf number and GCR intensity, according to which this growth in 2032 will be 2.6%.

Keywords: galactic cosmic rays, K-waves, Kondratiev cycles, J. Schumpeter, S.Yu. Glazyev, alpha waves of the brain, cognitive productivity, global GDP per capita, helioeconomics, long waves of economic activity, coefficient of determination, economic cycles.

Great scientists Frederick William Herschel, William Stanley Jevons, and Alexander Leonidovich Chizhevsky developed a methodological approach to studying the connections between solar and economic activity in their works.

For example, in his article "Solar-Commercial Cycles" W. S. Jevons placed graphs of solar activity cycles (Wolf number cycles) and corn price cycles in Delhi over the period 1760–1810 one after the other [4, p. 227]. That is, he compared solar and economic activity.

A. L. Chizhevsky in his monograph “The Cosmic Pulse of Life: Earth in the Embrace of the Sun” in Chapter 4 “The Sun and Epidemics” in Fig. 33 constructed a diagram that shows the average solar activity (SA) cycle (Wolf number cycle) over a hundred years and the average number of cholera cases in Russia for the period 1823-1923 [2, p. 201].

The annual mean Wolf numbers, the main indicator of solar activity, were taken from the well-known astrophysical website for the determination, conservation, and distribution of the international sunspot number [3]. They are presented in column 2 of Table 1.

The year numbers in column 3 of Table 1 are determined in accordance with the year numbering conventions used in solar astrophysics. Specifically, the first year in a solar cycle is considered to be the first year of its growth, i.e., the increase in the Wolf number. Subsequent years are numbered sequentially, and the last year in the cycle is considered to be the year of the Wolf number minimum.

Statistical data on GCR intensity were taken from the Moscow Neutron Monitor website [1]. They are presented in column 4 of Table 1.

The World Bank website [7] contains annual growth rates of global GDP per capita for the period 1961–2024. They are presented in column 5 of Table 1.

A two-year lag is necessary due to the natural inertia of human and production processes. The biological impulse of the GKL changes people's cognitive tone instantly, but its conversion into economic results requires months of developing ideas, finding investors, and signing contracts. This lag is completed by the purely physical time required to build factories, purchase equipment, and produce goods, which are then recorded in the final annual statistics of global GDP per capita.

Table 1. Years, average annual Wolf numbers (1959–2022), ordinal numbers of years in SA cycles, GCR intensity (1959–2022), and annual growth rates of world GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years (1961–2024)

1. Years	2. Wolf number (W)	3. The ordinal number of the year in the SA cycle	4. GCR intensity, imp/min	5. Annual growth rate of world GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years, %
1959	225.1	5	8241	2.56
1960	159	6	8795	3.48
1961	76.4	7	8979	2.81
1962	53.4	8	9179	4.39
1963	39.9	9	9422	3.43
1964	15	10	9591	3.23
1965	22	1	9275	1.63
1966	66.8	2	8941	3.79
1967	132.9	3	8676	3.79
1968	150	4	8538	1.64
1969	149.4	5	8625	2.00
1970	148	6	9118	3.46
1971	94.4	7	9279	4.35
1972	97.6	8	9236	0.02
1973	54.1	9	9151	-1.22
1974	49.2	10	9252	3.31
1975	22.5	11	9313	2.20
1976	18.4	12	9441	2.30
1977	39.3	1	9127	2.29
1978	131	2	8644	0.08
1979	220.1	3	8446	0.12
1980	218.9	4	8095	-1.43
1981	198.9	5	8078	0.74

1982	162.4	6	8376	2.87
1983	91	7	8536	1.86
1984	60.5	8	9029	1.47
1985	20.6	9	9342	1.87
1986	14.8	10	9329	2.68
1987	33.9	1	8753	1.87
1988	123	2	7925	0.96
1989	211.1	3	7859	-0.44
1990	191.8	4	7869	0.43
1991	203.3	5	8537	0,29
1992	133	6	8912	1.82
1993	76.1	7	9015	1.62
1994	44.9	8	9198	2.06
1995	25.1	9	9269	2.45
1996	11.6	10	9282	1.36
1997	28.9	1	9086	2.14
1998	88.3	2	8760	3.14
1999	136.3	3	8263	0.68
2000	173.9	4	8409	0.98
2001	170.4	5	8352	1.77
2002	163.6	6	8214	3.17
2003	99.3	7	8609	2.74
2004	65.3	8	8680	3.16
2005	45.8	9	9291	3.11
2006	24.7	10	9464	0.81
2007	12.6	11	9525	-2.55
2008	4.2	12	9670	3.26
2009	4.8	1	9414	2.09
2010	24.9	2	9202	1.45

2011	80.8	3	9083	1.63
2012	84.5	4	8998	1.90
2013	94	5	8915	1.90
2014	113.3	6	8927	1.60
2015	69.8	7	9361	2.29
2016	39.8	8	9548	2.16
2017	21.7	9	9637	1.61
2018	7	10	9699	-3.85
2019	3.6	11	9734	5.53
2020	8.8	1	9655	2.51
2021	29.6	2	9287	2.00
2022	83.2	3	8719	1.89
2023	125.5	4	8424	N/A
2024	154.6	5	8245	N/A
2025	123.2	6	Н.д.	N/A
2026	N/A	7	Н.д.	N/A

Note: 2024 is a year with a high probability of minimum GCR intensity.

The following table 2 is compiled based on the data in table 1 by selecting the rows with the GCR intensity maxima.

Table 2. Years of maximum GCR intensity and global GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years

1. Line number	2. Year of maximum GCR intensity	3. GCR intensity in the year of their maximum, imp/min	4. Annual growth rate of world GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years, %
1	1964	9591	3.235
2	1976	9441	2.302
3	1985	9342	1.874
4	1996	9282	1.364
5	2008	9670	3.260
6	2019	9734	5.530
Correlation coefficient: rows 1–6, columns 3 and 4:			0.916

For a correlation coefficient of $R = 0.916$ with a sample size of $n = 6$, $p = 0.0103$ or 1.03%. Since $p = 0.0103 < 0.05$, the randomness of the data in columns 3 and 4 of Table 4 is refuted. There is only a 1% probability that such a strong relationship between cosmic rays and global GDP per capita with a 2-year lag in this table arose purely by chance.

A diagram based on rows 1–6 and columns 2, 3, and 4 of Table 4 is constructed in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Large waves of GCR intensity in the years of their maximums and global GDP with a lag of 2 years

Based on columns 3 and 4 of Table 4, the following diagram is constructed in Fig. 5.

Рис. 2. Интенсивность ГКЛ в год их максимумов и мировой ВВП на душу населения с лагом в 2 года

The mechanism by which GCR intensity influences the economy (see Fig. 1) is as follows. During years of GCR maxima, solar activity is at its lowest (this is an established law of nature, see Fig. 3) and geomagnetic activity is at its lowest.

Source: data from Table 1

Fig. 3. Very strong feedback between GCR intensity and solar activity (Wolf numbers) by years of the average (12 years) solar cycle, using the superposition method of epochs

High geomagnetic activity inhibits processes in the brain. A fundamental study by scientists at the California Institute of Technology (Caltech) led by K. Wang and J. Kirschvink, "Transduction of the Geomagnetic Field as Evidenced from Alpha-band Activity in the Human Brain" (2019) [6], experimentally demonstrated that the human brain subconsciously responds to magnetic triggers, resulting in desynchronization and suppression of alpha waves.

Alpha waves are responsible for a state of calm wakefulness, creativity, intuition, and information integration. When geomagnetic activity suppresses them (causing desynchronization), humanity collectively enters a state of subconscious stress, brain "noise," and decreased cognitive potential. This leads to a decline in the effectiveness of human mental

activity and a reduction in the number and effectiveness of new technological paradigms. The result is a decline in the global per capita GDP growth rate as a percentage of the previous year.

The lower the GCR intensity, the higher the SA and geomagnetic activity, the more the processes in the brain are inhibited, the less productive mental activity is, and the less effective technological innovations and their impact on global GDP per capita as a % of the previous year (see the minimum GCR intensity in Fig. 2).

The peak cosmic ray intensity is a marker of ideal "magnetic silence" on Earth. In this silence, the human brain functions undisturbed in optimal alpha mode, which enhances the quality of humanity's intellectual capital, generates innovation and new technological paradigms, and advances the global economy (see the peak cosmic ray intensity in Fig. 2).

The prevailing scientific concept of new technological paradigms (for example, that of S. Yu. Glazyev) views innovation as the root cause of K-waves. However, it is powerless to explain the cyclical nature of these paradigms themselves.

If Nikolai Kondratiev associated the nature of long waves with the renewal of fixed capital, Joseph Schumpeter with the wave-like formation of innovation clusters, and Sergei Glazyev with the periodic change of technological paradigms, then my theory asserts: the cyclical nature of all these processes is a consequence of the cyclical nature of the human brain's productivity, which is modulated by the cosmos and, above all, by the cyclical nature of geomagnetic disturbances."

To forecast the K-wave, one should use the NASA long-term forecast of solar activity minimum [5]. This forecast is presented in Fig. 4 and shows that the next SA minimum (and GCR maximum) is expected in 2030. According to my calculations, its value for the 50% percentile is 10.82, and in the diagram in Fig. 3, it corresponds to a GCR intensity of 9550 cpm, which in the diagram in Fig. 2 corresponds to a growth rate of global GDP per capita in 2032 of 2.6%.

Therefore, in the diagram in Fig. 1 we can add the forecast of the development of the K-wave (see Fig. 5).

Fig. 4. Forecast of the development of the current 25th cycle of solar activity

Fig. 5. Forecast of the development of the K-wave of annual growth of global GDP per capita

The following Table 3 is compiled based on the selection of GCR intensity extremum values from Table 1.

Table 3. Years of GCR intensity extremes and annual growth of global GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years

1.Line number	2. Year of extreme GCR intensity	3. GCR intensity in the year of their maximum, imp/min	4 Annual growth rate of world GDP per capita with a lag of 2 years, %
1	1964	9591	3.235
2	1968	8538	1.64
3	1976	9441	2.302
4	1981	8078	0.74
5	1985	9342	1.874
6	1989	7859	-0.44
7	1996	9282	1.364
8	2002	8214	3.17
9	2008	9670	3.260
10	2013	8915	1.90
11	2019	9734	5.530
Correlation coefficient: rows 1–11, columns 3 and 4:			0.68

Based on rows 1–11 and columns 3 and 4 of Table 3, Figure 6 constructs the following diagram. For the presented polynomial model, $p = 0.0099$. Since $p < 0.01$, this nonlinear relationship is highly significant (reliability exceeds 99%), and the fourth-degree polynomial explains 86.16% of the variance in annual global GDP growth with a 2-year lag.

Fig. 6. Extremes of GCR intensity and annual growth of global GDP with a lag of 2 years

The left side of the diagram in Figure 6 is characterized by the following features:

1. Low GCR intensity;
2. High solar and geomagnetic activity;
3. Maximum subconscious alpha wave suppression, collective stress, and hemispheric desynchronization;
4. Chronic deficit of breakthrough innovations;
5. Low or negative annual growth rates of global GDP per capita with a two-year lag.

The right side of the diagram in Fig. 6 is characterized by the following features:

1. Maximum GCR intensity;
2. Minimum solar and geomagnetic activity;
3. Brain function in ideal alpha mode, peak creativity, intuition, and knowledge integration.
4. The emergence of new technological paradigms, a sharp increase in global GDP per capita with a two-year lag.

Ultimately, the work proves that the nature of K-waves has a cosmic origin: solar and magnetic activity cyclically influence the productivity of the human brain, setting the pace of innovation and the growth of global GDP per capita.

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